

Critical thinking in Design and technology (D&T)

The challenge in defining critical thinking

Critical thinking is a multi-layered construct (Willingham, 2020), and whilst various researchers have offered diverse definitions to capture its complexity and depth, it has been suggested that critical thinking is hard to distinguish with one clear definition (Ab Kadir 2018; Wei 2020; Yang 2009).

Ennis (1987, 1996, 2018) emphasised the importance of fostering critical thinking skills early in education, highlighting its influence on cognitive development and problem-solving abilities. Facione's (1990, 2000) work on critical thinking pedagogy stresses the importance of implementing strategies that encourage active student engagement, reasoning, and problem-solving.

Lai (2011) and Barnett (1997) have the view that defining the concept of critical thinking is dependent upon how it is used. Lai refers to Bloom's (1956) taxonomy of learning, critical thinking being one of the higher-order thinking skills and Barnett identifies four different ways of utilising the skill: as a stand-alone discipline, as knowledge used practically, engaged politically and as strategic thinking (p.10-14).

Separating critical and creative thinking

Vincent-Lancrin et al. (2019) suggests the difference between the two cognitive skills are that "critical thinking is mainly inquisitive, a detective way of thinking; creative thinking is imaginative, the artist way of thinking" (2019, p.27).

Spuzic et al. (2016) determines that within engineering, criticality and creativity are valuable skills. Whilst creative thinking can be seen as imaginative and critical thinking more analytical, both have worth in design and engineering (p.3). The report cites Adriansen (2010) table that attempts to differentiate the two cognitive skills.

Table 1: Idealised differences between criticality and creativity

Creativity	Criticality
Imaginative	Rational
Non-judgemental	Evaluative
Generative	Selective
Holistic	Analytical
Constructing	Deconstructing
Transcending the framework	Within the framework
Open to serendipity	Work systematically
Iterative process with detours	Linear process

Taken from Table 1 Spuzic et al (2016, p.5)

Critical thinking in D&T

Wei Long's (2020) research underscores the significant impact of hands-on learning experiences in promoting critical thinking among students, which is particularly relevant to the context of D&T education. There are other researchers that link this metacognitive skill as being synonymous with the subject of D&T, for example Rauscher and Badenhorst (2021).

Whilst other significant studies related to critical thinking (Halpern (2002), Mulnix (2012), Nicholl (2017), Cáceres, M., Nussbaum, M., & Ortiz, J. (2020)) concur with the positivity of critical thinking in D&T activities, a gap exists in understanding how these theories and findings translate into practice. Furthermore, considering the multitude of differing descriptions of critical thinking, many researchers mentioned above agree that critical thinking is hard to quantify, to define and to assess.

Why to teach critical thinking

Erikson's (2019) research on the significance of vocational education in fostering a skilled workforce underscores the relevance of aligning D&T education with future career prospects for young learners. This highlights how teaching critical thinking within D&T can equip students with both foundational skills and practical knowledge that are essential for their future endeavours.

Vincent-Lancrin et al. (2019) states that critical and creative thinking are two skills necessary for the future workforce and that critical thinking in particular can “contribute to human well-being and to the good functioning of democratic societies” (2019, p.18). the authors also suggest that critical thinking has become even more vital “in a digital world in which a multiplicity of facts, views, theories and assumptions compete” (2019, p.20).

An independent panel, led by David Sainsbury for the DfE, states “our education and skills system is failing to develop the skills employers seek” (DfE, 2016, p.22). Furthermore, Jagannathan et al. (2019), stated that future employers seek employees who demonstrate skills “critical thinking and design thinking and negotiation skills which contribute to complex problem-solving in the workplace” (2019, p.2).

This can be supported by research from around the world. Trilling and Foden (2009) in the USA, Ab Kadir (2018) in Australia and a Chilean based study by Cáceres et al. (2020, p.1) cite and agree with Butler et al. (2017) suggesting that “mastering critical thinking is a better predictor of successful life decisions than other factors, such as intelligence.”

Best practice for critical thinking

Whilst the literature may demonstrate the benefits of critical thinking, the ‘how’ to teach it is more challenging. Willingham (2000) suggests a four-stage strategy to introduce and develop critical thinking skills with children and young people.

- Identify critical thinking skills in each domain: skills are subject and skill dependent.

- Identify the domain content students must know: specific knowledge is required before considering it critically.
- Sequencing critical thinking skills: a sequential development of thinking skills.
- Revisiting critical thinking skills: retention of critical thinking skills.

Conclusion

The above research highlights that just exposing students to opportunities for critical thinking is not enough, it needs to be considered long term and continually revisited. Teachers of D&T therefore need to consider the importance of teaching, modelling and providing opportunities for developing critical thinking skills with students of all abilities and ages.

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